

ACOUSTIC EMISSION CHARACTERIZATION OF FRACTURE PROCESS OF SiC/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Acoustic emission was used to clarify fatigue failure mechanisms of aluminium alloys reinforced with SiC particulate(SiCp/A356) or whisker(SiCw/Al2009). For this purpose, special attention was given to AE characteristics including AE event, energy and peak amplitude distribution which were associated with micro-fracture processes of metal matrix composites under the cyclic loading. The effects of form of reinforcements, heat treatment, orientation of whisker and loading condition on AE characteristics were discussed based on SEM fractographic results.

Keywords: Metal Matrix Composites, AE Parameters, Fracture Process, Fractography

1. INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites offer significant increase in elastic modulus and strength as well as improved resistance to fatigue initiation, creep and wear[1-2]. The typical examples of materials attracting enormous interest recently are aluminium alloys reinforced with SiC in particulate or whisker form which are receiving a great deal of attention for applications in the aerospace, automotive industries. For the successful application of metal matrix composites(MMCs) in these field, it is very important to understand micro-failure mechanism of the materials because failure mechanism of MMCs is dominated by cumulation of micro-failure due to applied loading. However, the substantial failure mechanisms of a discontinuously reinforced MMC depend strongly upon many factors such as the loading conditions, matrix material properties, the aspect ratio, the orientation and the volume fraction of reinforcement.

There have been a number of studies on the fracture and the strengthening mechanisms of more common powder processed MMCs such as SiC/Al and Al₂O₃/Al composites[3-4]. However, most of them were concerned with mechanical behaviors under static loading. On the other hand, many applications for which these materials can be considered involve cyclic loading and therefore, fatigue failure mechanism are also of critical interest from point of view of practical application. Micro-failure mechanisms due to cyclic loading in MMCs are much more complicated

than and substantially different from those under the static loading including the main processes of void nucleation and coalescence at the SiC/matrix interface[5], cracking of SiC particles[6] etc.,.

The objective of this work was to clarify failure mechanisms under static and cyclic loadings by analyzing AE characteristics of aluminium alloys reinforced with SiC particulate(SiCp) or whisker(SiCw). For this purpose, AE characteristics including AE events, energy and peak amplitude distributions were discussed on the basis of the following main macroscopic effects considering SEM fractographic results;

- form of reinforcements(SiCp and SiCw)
- heat treatment
- orientation(L-T or T-L)
- loading condition(cyclic or static)

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Materials and Specimen

The materials employed in this work were two kinds of aluminium alloy reinforced with SiC. One was A356 Al(Al-7Si-0.35Mg)composites reinforced with 15 pct volume fraction SiC particulates, produced by the molten metal mixing method by DURALCAN(A division of Alcan Aluminium, Inc.), San Diego, C.A., U.S.A. The size of the reinforcing SiC particulates ranged from 6 to 13 μm . The typical microstructures of these composites showed that reinforcing SiC particles in the composite are largely segregated in the intercellular regions. The other one was 15 pct volume fraction whisker-reinforced Al(2009) metal matrix composite fabricated by powder metallurgy technique by Advanced Composite Materials Corporation.

In order to study the effect of heat treatment on AE characteristics in MMCs, a part of materials were treated to T6 condition: that is, held for 8 hours at 540 °C followed by the water-quenching and 155 °C artificial aging for 16 hours for SiCp/A356 composites and also held for 495 °C for 2 hours following water quenching and 177 °C aging for 4 hours for SiCw/Al2009 composites.

Compact tension(CT) specimens with the thickness of 10 mm were prepared in both L-T and T-L direction with regard to the rolling direction.

2.2. Mechanical test

Fatigue tests were performed for both as-fabricated and T6 treated materials at room temperature under a repetition of sine loading wave with the frequency 5 Hz using a biaxial servohydraulic testing machine. The maximum load was 2.0 kN and the stress ratio was 0.1. Tensile tests were also carried out for fatigue cracked specimen under cyclic loading to compare AE characteristics with those obtained under fatigue loading.

2.3. Acoustic Emission Measurement

An AE sensor with 300kHz resonant frequency (MAC300L, AET Corp.) was attached to the side surface normal to the notch direction. Detected signals were amplified by 60dB with 250kHz-500kHz bandpass filtering then connected to the IBM/AT interfaced AE instrumentation(5500, AET Corp.). The threshold level was set to 200 μV at the sensor. The rms voltage and the digital

AE waveforms were also recorded by using an RMS voltmeter(HP 3400A) and a digital oscilloscope (DATA6100 Analogic),respectively.The schematic diagram of experimental setup is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of Instrumentation

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Fractography under Cyclic Loading

It was well recognized that the addition of SiCp or SiCw generally improved fatigue lifetimes over those of the unreinforced at a constant stress. However, the roles of particulate and whisker on mechanisms of fatigue crack initiation and propagation are slightly different in MMCs. At the initial stage of cyclic loading for the SiCp/A356 composites, the cyclic hardening is occurred at SiC particles associated with the pile-up of dislocation density. Once dislocation density around SiC particle has been reached to critical value, fatigue microcracks originated at a large SiC particles or clusters of SiC particles. The next process is related to linkage of microcracks as shown in Photo.1(a). It is revealed from striation('A') in Photo.1(a) that the microcrack initiated around SiC particle is linked up with that formed eutectic Si particle. In SiCp/A356 composite, strains in SiC particles with plastic zone formed at notch tip of specimen were generally found to be large,with the accompanying high stresses caused by only elastic deformation. This results in a very large gradient at the particle/matrix interface which makes it difficult to define a debonding stress. However, as the number of cycle is increased, voids or microcracks formed around SiC particles are eventually linked to the main crack.

Fracture surface of SiCw/Al2009 with L-T orientation subjected to the cyclic loading was illustrated in Photo.1(c),which exhibits quasi-cleavage fracture region('C') and a isolated patch of striation('B'). In the L-T orientation, the whiskers are at right angles to the fracture plane with their axes normal to the direction of crack propagation. Decohesion of the whisker/matrix interface is observed and presence of this weak interface at right angles to the macroscopic direction of crack propagation causes repeated local deflection of the crack into short transverse plane. However, in the T-L orientation as shown in Photo.1(d), the whisker platelets are oriented at rihft angles to the fracture plane with their major axes running in the direction of crack propagation. The fracture surfaces show evidence of decohesion of the whisker/interfaces in the thickness direction,this resulting in the development of numerous parallel splits running in the direction of crack propagation.

3.2. Fractography under Static Loading

It is generally accepted that a ductile fracture in the presence of second-phase particles occurs by nucleation of voids at the particles, growth of these voids, and their coalence which manifests the actual physical seperation. The ductility of the material is determined by the extent of the void grow. From the results of SEM observation, the void growth stage was very limited for SiCp/A356 because of its inherent brittleness of cast A356Al. Fracture surface of tensile specimen of

(c)

(d)

Photo.1. SEM fractograph of fracture surfaces (a) SiCp/A356 under fatigue loading (b) SiCp/A356 under static loading (c) SiCw/Al 2009 under fatigue loading (L-T) (d) SiCw/Al 2009 under fatigue loading (T-L)

Fig.2 AE results for the particulate type specimen(SiC_p-T6)
 (a) AE event vs. time
 (b) energy distribution
 (c) peak amplitude distribution

Fig.3 AE results for the whisker type specimen(SiC_w-T6/L-T)
 (a) AE event vs. time
 (b) energy distribution
 (c) peak amplitude distribution

SiC_p/A356 composites in the intercellular regions with the cluster of SiC particles was shown in Fig.2(b), which revealed the brittle fracture mode, together with a very small amount of dimple fracture and interfacial decohesions of SiC particles. It is noted that brittle fracture mode observed in Photo.1(b) is attributed to premature failure of the brittle intercellular clusters.

3.3. Type of Reinforcements - Particulate vs. Whisker

Particulate- and whisker-MMCs showed very different AE behavior as shown in Fig.2(a) and Fig.3(a), respectively. Generally, particulate MMC showed very low AE event rate than whisker MMC did. The overall event rate was less than 10 events/min for particulate types whereas it reached to 100-150 events/min for whisker types. AE events for particulate MMC occurred randomly in the early stage of cyclic loading but the rate increased gradually as the crack initiated as shown in Fig.2(a). Two distinct peaks were observed in the energy distribution but a single peak in the peak amplitude distribution. This indicates that the signals were composed of two types with almost similar amplitude but different signal duration.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.4 AE results for the as-fabricated SiC_w specimen
 (a) AE event vs. time
 (b) energy distribution
 (c) peak amplitude distribution

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.5 AE results for the whisker type specimen(SiC_w-T6/T-L)
 (a) AE event vs. time
 (b) energy distribution
 (c) peak amplitude distribution

In contrast to particulate MMC, whisker MMC reveals peculiar characteristics in AE events vs. loading cycles. The AE events vs. time curve shows periodic bumps of AE events with about 30 minute intervals as shown in Fig.3(a). It was speculated that the initiation of microcracks in the plastic zone by the cyclic loading accompanied with the increased rate of AE events and the coalescence between microcracks resulted in the crack growth. For this growth the strain energy was almost exhausted, therefore AE event rate decreased until a sufficient amount of strain energy is stored to initiate new microcracks. This phenomena would be repeated several times.

Some differences were also found in AE behaviors of whisker- and particulate-MMC from the energy distribution but not from the peak amplitude distribution as shown in Fig.2(b),(c) and Fig.3(b),(c). Extra peaks centered at 66 and 80 of energy distribution as compared with that of particulate MMC, which were thought to be the unique characteristics of whisker reinforced materials. It is concluded that whisker MMC probably has several types of AE sources compared to particulate MMC.

(a)

(b)

(a)

(b)

Fig.6 AE results for particulate type specimen under static loading

Fig.7 AE event vs. time for whisker type specimen under static loading

3.4. Effect of Heat Treatment

The effect of heat treatment on AE behaviors can be explained by comparing data from the as-fabricated with that of the T6 condition, namely Fig.4 with Fig.3. The total number of events from as-fabricated material is much lower than that of the T6 condition. The initial stage of cyclic loading with relatively low rate of AE events for 2 hours was followed by the incubation period with virtually no AE event for 1 hour, then the rate of AE events suddenly increased as shown in Fig.4(a). The sudden increase in AE events implied the initiation of main crack, which was actually confirmed by traveling microscope observation. The incubation period can be regarded as the period of strain hardening or expanding plastic zone. From these results, it appeared that a strong bonding or the constraint is developed at the whisker/matrix interface by heat treatment, which would develop the conditions necessary to activate numerous AE sources.

3.5. Effect of Orientation (L-T/T-L)

In whisker MMC, the effect of whisker orientation on mechanical properties is substantial. The results of AE data for T-L orientation specimens comparing to L-T orientation specimens are shown in Fig.5(a),(b),(c). The T-L specimen showed very low AE event rate comparing to L-T specimen as shown in Fig.5(a). The rate were 110-130 events/min for L-T and 30 events/min for T-L specimens. The existence of whiskers and their orientation primarily account for this difference. In L-T geometry, whiskers are oriented perpendicular to the notch and the prospective crack propagation so that the crack is deflected and propagated through the whisker/matrix interface as discussed in fractography section. Numerous microcracks or debondings at the interface ahead of main crack tip account for the higher rate of AE events. On the other hand, whiskers are oriented parallel to the prospective crack propagation so that once the main crack was observed it propagated in an unstable fashion in T-L geometry. The main crack was initiated and observed at about 30 minutes of cyclic loading and the specimen failed in less than 10 minutes after the crack

was observed. The overall rate of AE events was very low since not as many interfaces as in the case of L-T orientation were undergone the debonding or microcracking process in T-L orientation.

Although the rate of AE events was much lower than in the L-T orientation, most of the AE events were very energetic in T-L orientation. Comparing to the Gaussian-like distribution of Fig.3(b),(c) for L-T orientation, the peak amplitude and the energy distribution of AE events for T-L orientation as shown in Fig.5(b),(c) indicated several unique peaks. Note that the high energy events centered at 85dB in Fig.5(b) and the high amplitude events centered at 58dB in Fig.5(c). These characteristics were attributed to the rapid crack growth or unstable crack propagation in T-L specimens.

3.6. Cyclic vs. Static Loading

AE behaviors of both MMCs under static loading were investigated by tensile loading of the precracked specimens through the cyclic loading above. AE events vs. time curves are shown in Fig.6(a) and Fig.7(a) for particulate- and whisker-MMCs, respectively. As in the cyclic loading the whisker MMC showed almost one order of magnitude higher rate of AE events than the particulate MMC did. Since the maximum load level during the cyclic loading was 2.0kN, the Kaiser effect was well observed for both MMCs.

Under the static loading, both MMCs generated relatively low amplitude and low energy AE events as shown in Fig.6(b) and Fig.7(b). On the other hand, a significant portion of AE events during the cyclic loading showed high amplitude and high energy especially for whisker MMC as shown in Fig.3(b),(c). This can be speculated that materials under the cyclic loading behave more brittle fashion than under the static loading. It is also confirmed by the SEM fractographs as shown in Photo.1(b) and Photo.1(c) by the observation of a dimple dominant and a quasi-cleavage dominant structures. The cleavage or quasi-cleavage fracture process is generally known as the source of energetic AE events in other materials[7]. It was concluded that the MMCs under cyclic loading emitted broader range of AE signals with a significant portion of highly energetic events which were attributed to the quasi-cleavage fracture process.

4. CONCLUSION

Clear differences were found in AE behaviors of SiCp and SiCw MMCs from the AE event, the peak and the energy distribution. The total number of events from the as-fabricated materials is much lower than that of the T6 condition. This might be due to the strong bonding or the constraint effect produced by heat treatment. The T-L specimen showed very low AE event rate comparing to L-T specimen. For T-L orientation, the peak amplitude and energy distribution of AE events indicated several unique peaks which were attributed to the unstable crack propagation. The MMCs under cyclic loading emitted broader range of AE signal with a significant portion of highly energetic events which were attributed to the quasi-cleavage fracture process.

It is recommended that future work on AE waveform analysis using the broad band type sensor is necessary to get a better understanding of micro-failure mechanism, especially to understand the effect of microscopic material parameters of MMCs.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by NON DIRECTED RESEARCH FUND, Korea Research Foundation, 1992.

6. REFERENCES

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